

Chaotic dynamics and sensitivity of auditory detection

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Abstract. Hair cells of the auditory system constitute a remarkable biological sensor that exhibits nanometer-scale sensitivity of mechanical detection. Simultaneously, this detection must show high temporal acuity, as to allow the localization of sound. We propose that the innate dynamics of hair cells support chaotic dynamics, which allow the response to be both sensitive and rapid. This presentation will focus on a summary of theoretical results that explore the relative benefits of criticality and chaos, specifically in terms of their impact on sensitivity, frequency selectivity, temporal acuity, and robustness to noise, observed in the hair cell response. An overview of experimental results will focus on the current evidence that indicates the presence of chaos in active hair bundle motility. Finally, we will include our results showing that efferent neurons serve as a gain control system, strongly affecting the response of the mechanosensory cell.

INTRODUCTION

The sense of hearing constitutes a crucial sensory system for a broad range of animal species, enabling navigation in space, localization of prey, avoidance of predators, and communication with conspecifics. The first step in the processing of auditory information by the inner ear is performed by hair cells, sensory cells that convert mechanical displacements into electrical signals, which can then be conveyed to the brain [1]. These mechanosensitive hair cells of the inner ear have been shown to be highly nonlinear detectors that extract sub-nanometer signals amidst higher levels of noise. The auditory system furthermore expends energy to amplify incoming signals, and this active process was shown to be crucial in maintaining the acuity of hearing [2]. While much progress has been made in unraveling the cellular processes and the identity of molecules behind this detection and amplification, many important questions remain open, which may apply to other mechanical and sensory systems. Specifically, the manner in which a sensory cell can extract minute signals from ambient biological noise has not been fully explained.

Auditory and vestibular hair cells from a number of species have been shown to operate under nonequilibrium conditions, in which they expend energy to maintain cyclic steady-state dynamics [3]. Empirical studies have established that an internal active amplifier underlies spontaneous oscillations, which require the expenditure of energy to overcome the viscous damping by the surrounding fluid. In one application of nonequilibrium thermodynamics to the study of hearing, comparisons to the fluctuation dissipation theorem have rigorously proven these oscillations to be active [4].

Prior studies have shown that these active limit cycle oscillations exhibit some of the classical features of nonlinear oscillators. Specifically, they can undergo transitions in their dynamic state, with different bifurcations characterizing various regions of phase space. Proximity to these critical points can yield numerous advantages in the detection characteristics, including high sensitivity and frequency selectivity of the response. In particular, the supercritical Hopf bifurcation, inspired by the cubic nonlinearities in hearing, has been shown to capture many of the experimental phenomena [5].

In our recent studies, we have extended this theoretical framework to address the conundrum of how the auditory system achieves high temporal resolution in conjunction with its sensitivity. Many animal species exhibit inter-aural time resolution in the range of ten microseconds, a feature key to the ability to localize auditory sources in space. As proximity to a bifurcation point results in critical slowing down, it introduces a highly undesirable tradeoff between detection of weak signals and speed of response. Chaos is characterized by dynamics that are extremely sensitive to perturbations: even minute differences in the initial conditions lead to an exponential divergence of trajectories of the system [6]. Further, its speed of response is set by the value of the Lyapunov exponent, and hence improves with chaoticity. Sensitivity of the auditory system to external perturbations and its speed of response therefore suggest the possibility that hair cells may be exploiting chaotic dynamics to avoid the tradeoff.

FIGURE 1. (a-c) Poincaré maps constructed from the time intervals between the steepest rising flanks of consecutive hair bundle oscillations under low ($175\mu M$), natural ($250\mu M$), and high ($325\mu M$) calcium concentrations of the endolymph. Recordings were obtained during presentation of an off-resonance sinusoidal stimulus of ~ 12 pN amplitude. (d) Circle map corresponding to the low-calcium conditions. The monotonic function suggests the absence of chaos. (e-f) Circle maps corresponding to the natural- and high-calcium conditions, respectively. The absence of a monotonic function in e and f indicates torus breakdown, one of the signatures of the presence of a chaotic attractor. We use Spearman's rank correlation coefficient to test for monotonicity of the circle maps. Under low-, natural-, and high-calcium conditions, Spearman's coefficient is 0.60, 0.14, and 0.30, respectively. All of the recordings were obtained from hair bundles of the bullfrog sacculus, maintained in a two-compartment chamber. Reproduced from ref. [8] by permission of the authors.

EXPERIMENTAL EVIDENCE FOR A CHAOTIC ATTRACTOR

Prior studies performed in our group demonstrated the presence of a chaotic attractor in biologically functional hair cells, showing clear signatures of torus breakdown, as well as other analytical measures obtained from the innate and driven bundle motility [7]. Furthermore, since previous experiments have demonstrated that internal Ca^{2+} concentration plays an important role in shaping hair bundle dynamics, we explored its impact on the innate chaoticity of spontaneous oscillations. Our observations showed that indeed, manipulation of Ca^{2+} ions in the surrounding fluids could reduce, enhance, or entirely eliminate the presence of deterministic noise in the hair bundle motility. This ability to modulate the degree of chaos of hair cells experimentally allowed us to show that sensitivity of detection is indeed enhanced in the weakly chaotic regime [8]. Further, the temporal resolution of the system's response to a transient stimulus was shown to significantly increase with chaoticity.

THEORETICAL COMPARISON OF CRITICALITY VERSUS CHAOS

In recent theoretical studies, we explored how the existing framework for auditory dynamics, based on the supercritical Hopf bifurcation [5], can be extended to include chaotic dynamics. For example, inclusion of a self-tuning equation, one which allows the system to poise itself near critical oscillation, was shown to support chaos [9]. Alternatively, an even simpler generalization can be introduced into the differential equations for the Hopf oscillator:

in the presence of noise, very different behavior can be observed in the response of an isochronous Hopf oscillator versus a nonisochronous one, in which the frequency of oscillation depends on its amplitude [8]. In the latter case, the introduction of stochastic noise into the theoretical model renders the dynamics chaotic, whereas the isochronous case shows noisy but stable limit cycle oscillation.

The theoretical model we explored is given by the following equation:

$$\frac{dz}{dt} = (\mu + i\omega_0)z - (\alpha + i\beta)|z|^2z + F(t) + \eta(t), \quad (1)$$

where $z(t)$ describes the dynamics of hair bundle motility. The real component, $x(t) = \text{Re}[z(t)]$, describes the time-dependent position of the hair bundle, while the imaginary component reflects the internal active process of the bundle. The symbols μ and ω_0 denote the control parameter and characteristic frequency of the detector, respectively. The parameters α and β are introduced to characterize the nonlinearity of the system, $F(t)$ represents the external forcing on the system, while $\eta(t)$ is a stochastic variable, representing thermal noise.

The parameter β has been shown to play an important role in shaping the oscillatory solutions to this differential equation. If $\beta = 0$, the system is isochronous, meaning that the amplitude of the limit cycle oscillation and its frequency are independent of each other. When the parameter is nonzero, the amplitude of the oscillation affects the frequency, and the two degrees of freedom are thus mixed. It has been shown in prior literature that a nonisochronous system can exhibit chaos in the presence of noise. Dependent on the choices of μ , the control parameter, and β , the term quantifying the nonisochronicity, the system can be poised either in the chaotic, stable limit cycle, or fixed-point regime. The simple framework hence allows us to explore the full phase space of hair cell dynamics, and determine the impact of chaos on the detection characteristics.

The full set of theoretical results yields a gamut of effects, indicating that chaos affects the dynamic range of nonlinear response, robustness to external noise, quality factor, ability to extract information from amplitude and frequency modulation, etc. In Figure 2, we focus on two main metrics: sensitivity of mechanical detection, defined as the phase-locked amplitude of hair bundle oscillation divided by the force of the applied signal, and the time constant of the response, extracted from the return of a hair bundle to its steady-state position upon cessation of a step signal.

Consistent with the experimental results, our theoretical exploration indicated that the weakly chaotic regime yields the highest sensitivity of mechanical detection. Furthermore, increasing levels of chaos led to faster temporal resolution of the system. We hence propose that chaotic dynamics may underlie the ability of the auditory system to reconcile the need for sensitivity, in the presence of noise, with the rapid response of hearing observed *in vivo*.

EFFERENT CONTROL OF HAIR CELL DYNAMICS

Apart from its sensitivity, the delicate machinery of the inner ear needs to withstand intense signals, without sustaining immediate and irreparable damage. There are many indications that the efferent neurons serve as a complex gain control mechanism for hearing. While their mechanisms and impact are far from fully understood, efferents are believed to play an important role in maintaining the integrity of hearing and fine-tuning the detection properties. Specifically, a number of studies have shown that severing the efferent neurons leads to greater levels of ototoxicity. While efferent effects have been explored *in vivo* and shown to have a significant and multi-faceted impact on hearing, previously there was little known of how efference impacts the mechanical sensitivity of the hair bundle.

We demonstrated that efferent activation leads to significant changes in the mechanical response already at the level of an individual hair cell [10]. An *in vitro* preparation was developed that maintained the innervation of the sensory epithelium, allowing us to stimulate efferent neurons in conjunction with mechanical probing of the hair bundle response. Full maps of the hair cell's mechanical sensitivity were obtained, with stimuli spanning the physiological range of frequencies and amplitudes. Under efferent stimulus, the response was clearly and strongly reduced, across all levels and regimes of the applied signal. The efferent feedback was therefore shown to exert a direct effect already at the most peripheral level of detection, that of mechanical responsiveness of an individual hair cell, affecting the very compliance of its stereociliary bundle.

Activation of the efferent neurons also strongly affected the frequency and amplitude of innate limit cycle oscillation exhibited by the hair bundle. In the context of the Hopf bifurcation model, these findings indicate that efference impacts the control parameter μ , the nonisochronicity parameter β , or both. We therefore hypothesize that the system of efferent neurons may constitute the biological feedback mechanism that controls the degree of chaoticity of the hair cell, and thus fine-tunes its dynamical state in response to the external environment.

FIGURE 2. Theoretical calculation showing the effects of chaos on the (A) sensitivity and (B) temporal resolution of the system. The sensitivity χ is defined as the ratio of the phase-locked amplitude of hair bundle oscillation and the force of the applied signal, evaluated at the characteristic frequency. The temporal resolution is measured as the inverse of the time constant characterizing the return of a bundle to steady-state position after the offset of a step signal. The blue, black, orange, red, and purple traces correspond to $\mu = -1, 0, 0.3, 1,$ and $2,$ respectively. The noise strength was set to 10^{-3} , following prior estimates [8]. Stochastic differential equations were solved using Heun’s method, with time steps ranging from $2\pi * 10^{-4}$ to $2\pi * 10^{-3}$.

FIGURE 3. The frequency of spontaneous oscillations increased immediately upon the onset of the efferent stimulus. The traces show spontaneous oscillations before, during, and after efferent modulation, obtained from three representative hair bundles, offset for clarity. The efferent stimulus is shown below the hair bundle position traces. For activation of the efferent neurons, the eighth cranial nerve was inserted into a suction electrode, while the epithelium containing the hair cells was mounted in a two-compartment chamber. The experimental protocols followed closely those described in [10].

CONCLUSIONS

Our theoretical and experimental studies have indicated that chaotic dynamics may underlie the high sensitivity of hair cell detection in the presence of noise. This regime was shown to lead to a very rapid response, thus providing a means of achieving high temporal resolution. Furthermore, we propose that the responsiveness and the dynamic state of the hair cell are not fixed entities, but are subject to continuous feedback control by the efferent system. While the measurements presented in the current manuscript have all been obtained from hair cells of the bullfrog sacculus, future studies will aim to test the generality of these findings by exploring auditory systems of amphibian and other species.

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COMMENTS AND QUESTIONS

[Robert Fettiplace]: The paper attempts to account for the twin properties of the auditory system, high sensitivity and speed, in terms of a chaos theory. Measurements are based on the spontaneous oscillations of hair bundles in the frog saccule, sensitivity being assessed by the force/displacement behavior of free bundles and the speed by off time constant of return of a bundle to steady-state position after the offset of a step stimulus. A criticism is that it is unclear how these apply to the mammalian cochlea, where the speed is limited by the microsecond time constant of the mechanotransducer current, and the sensitivity is augmented post-transduction by the prestin motor in outer hair cells. Furthermore, It should be noted that the spontaneous bundle oscillations seen in the bullfrog saccule and not present in mammalian cochlear hair cells. These should be mentioned in the introduction. The Poincaré maps in Fig. 1a-c do not clearly exhibit chaotic behavior, and the plots in Fig.1 d-f all look approximately linear and monotonic, even though there is some low-level variability in Fig. 1f. Therefore, the conclusion of an "absence of a monotonic function, indicating the presence of chaos" is not accurate. The legend to Fig. 2 should indicate they are theoretical plots, and the labeling should be made larger on the abscissae and ordinate as they will be difficult to read. There is no description of this figure, and the significance of the dependence on beta is not obvious. What is meant by nonisochronicity? In terms of the efferent stimulation, the effects on the membrane conductance and electrical resonance to diminish the receptor potential are likely to be more important physiologically than the effects on bundle motion.

[Dolores Bozovic]: Robert, thank you for the suggestions and comments, they are very helpful. As our experimental data on this topic are from the bullfrog sacculus, we cannot generalize to the mammalian cochlea until such measurements are available. However, the problem of a tradeoff between sensitivity and speed of the response is ubiquitous in any dynamical system that operates in the vicinity of a critical point. In terms of theoretical models, such critical points can and do arise in systems where the amplification is ascribed either to hair bundle motility or prestin-based somatic motility, or both. Hence, we can speculate that chaotic dynamics may prove a general feature of these systems, but we cannot make such claim at this time. We have added a brief discussion of future studies to the end of the manuscript, as well as a clarification that our conclusions thus far apply only to the amphibian system. We have also clarified in the introduction that spontaneous oscillations have only been observed in nonmammalian species.

The plots of the Poincaré maps alone cannot immediately indicate the presence or absence of chaos; however, the plots of the corresponding circle maps below them do contain that information. The monotonicity of the function has rigorous mathematical tests, to distinguish it from mere noise, well established in mathematical literature. Hence, plots in parts (e) and (f) of Figure 1 indicate torus breakdown, whereas the plot in part (d) of the same figure

does not. While a thorough discussion of this methodology is too long to include in this manuscript, we have added some clarifications and reference to our prior work. We note that in previous publications, we performed a long set of other metrics to verify the presence of chaos, and found consistent results. Here, we focus on torus breakdown, as the consensus in the field is that it provides one of the most robust techniques when applied to data.

For the Figure 2, we have enlarged the labels and indicated that it is a theoretical plot. In the paragraphs following the Equation (1), we have added a discussion of the parameter β , a metric of nonisochronicity, its impact on the dynamics, and specifically its role in the occurrence of chaos.

Certainly, the role of efferent activation on the membrane conductance is important. The context in which we are interested in its impact on the bundle mechanics is two-fold. First, we aim to understand how it affects the sensitivity of the bundle, as it may be the biological mechanism that shapes the control parameters predicted by our theory. Our prior studies indicate that efferents vastly change the ability of the bundle to phase lock to a mechanical stimulus. Secondly, we are interested in its role as a protective mechanism, which can restore the sensitivity of a bundle, after it has been exposed to intense stimuli. Both of these questions relate to the effect of efferent stimulus on the active dynamics of the bundle explored in this study.

[Stephanie Gutschmidt]: Thank you Dolores and co-authors for sharing your inspiring work and results with the delegates of MoH2024. Your article suggests that the work presented here encompasses several years of research and expertise of your team. The results are very interesting and will stimulate important, meaningful discussions during the workshop to which I look forward to. My questions at this stage are more related to the details of model and experiment:

1) What is the dynamic bifurcation landscape of your model for control parameter(s)? Which parameter(s) do you track on the route to chaos?

2) Where does Eq (1) originate from? How does it relate to hair-cell dynamics, dynamic key features?

3) What were the choice of parameters (exp and simulation) with which Figures 1/2/3 were produced?

4) The quality of the manuscript would significantly improve if such and other details could be included. Furthermore, more of your previous work could be referred to, too?

[Dolores Bozovic]: Thank you, Stephanie, for the helpful comments.

1) The bifurcation landscape for the Normal Form Equation, which forms the basis of our model, is quite rich; the dominant bifurcations that shape the dynamics are the supercritical Hopf bifurcation and the saddle node bifurcation on an invariant circle (SNIC). The Bogdanov-Takens has also been observed in numerical simulations. Further, signatures of these have been found in experimental recordings of hair bundle motility. The parameters that we track in the model, to assess the onset of chaos and its impact of sensitivity, are the control parameter μ and the nonisochronicity parameter β .

2) The Equation (1) is the normal form equation for the supercritical Hopf bifurcation and has previously been proposed to describe the dynamics of the auditory system. The generalization we introduced in our prior work is the inclusion of the nonisochronicity term β . The motion of the hair bundle corresponds to the real component of the complex variable z . We have added these clarifications and references to the paragraphs preceding and following the equation.

3) For the experimental Figure 1, the only parameter that was varied is the calcium concentration of the endolymph, and in Figure 3, the recording shows the spontaneous oscillation only, with the specified efferent stimulus. We have added details on the experimental conditions for both of these recordings to the captions, as well as references to the prior work which elaborates on the experimental techniques. For the theoretical figure, the parameters μ and β were varied, with the values indicated in the figure and the caption; we have added the noise strength and time steps used in the simulation.

4) We agree and have included additional information in the paper. We have also added references to our prior work, each time that those results are used or mentioned in this manuscript.

[Jont Allen]: so, have you ever heard of Egbert de Boer?

[Dolores Bozovic]: I've heard of him, yeah.

[Jont Allen]: So, he wrote some papers on something called reverse correlation. He was a good friend. I tried to figure out what's going on. There was no question about the fact that what he was saying was true. The reverse correlation can take advantage of a nonlinear system, chaotic behavior, and get an equivalent impulse response that when you use that impulse response really does characterize the nonlinear system. Now, if you read his papers, you're going to learn a lot about what you're talking about here. I swear, and if you can't find it, I'll help you.

[Dolores Bozovic]: I will be delighted to look at his papers. Again, chaoticity to be proven in an experimental system is fairly difficult. I'm sure I'll be delighted to learn more.

[Jont Allen]: One short comment more. Every time there was an impulse on the auditory nerve, he saved the waveform, and then he averaged all those waveforms together and that gave him an impulse response.

[Dolores Bozovic]: Beautiful.